

Manohar Karanth P D

has successfully completed the AWS Certification requirements and has achieved their:

AWS Certified Machine Learning - Specialty

Issue Date

Oct 28, 2021

Expiration Date

Oct 28, 2024

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Maureen Lonergan".

Maureen Lonergan
Director, Training and Certification

Validation Number LM9LYLDJM1E4QB3V

Validate at: <http://aws.amazon.com/verification>